

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OBOUR****FIRST NAME: HUBERT****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 11%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2013 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR ACA-401D PERIOD 1 – ACA-401D PERIOD 2

1. As a general rule punctuation should be used as necessary while still retaining the, of the sentence.

Little, meaning.¹

Maximum, significance.

Little, importance.

Minimal, meaning.

2. American English is the dominant force in “world English” due to:

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021) 25.

- Population, economic power, education, publishing industry, global media influence, American popular culture, and the international status of the United States.²**
- Population, economic power, education, publishing industry, global media influence, American popular culture, and the local status of the United States.
- Population, economic power, education, publishing industry, global media influence, American niche, and the international status of the United States
- Population, economic power, ignorance, publishing industry, global media influence, American popular culture, and the international status of the United States
3. Citing your source is important for several reasons:
- Not only prevents plagiarism but also strengthens your argument and aids future research endeavors.**
- Giving credit, Ensuring accuracy, Demonstrating research tradition, and Facilitating further research.**
- All the above answers.³**
- None of the above answers.
4. What are the two criteria highlighted in the evaluation of usefulness of sources?
- Relevance and reliability.⁴**

² Ibid.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 139 – 140.

⁴ Ibid., 41 – 42.

- Clarity and conciseness.
 - Originality and uniqueness.
 - Accuracy and credibility.
5. When should abbreviations be used in academic writing?
- Only sparingly, as they can make the writing seem informal or too technical.**⁵
 - Frequently to make writing more concise.
 - Whenever local guidelines allow it regardless of the context.
 - Only in tables, figures, and citations, not in the main text.
6. What is the general rule for presenting numbers in humanities and social sciences?
- Spell out numbers from one through one hundred.**⁶
 - Use Arabic numerals for all numbers regardless of the value or context.
 - Use abbreviations for all numbers, including those numbers that are part of physical quantities.
 - Spell out all numbers regardless of their value and context.
7. How can collaboration with researchers benefit doctoral students in their research?
- All the answers below.**⁷
 - Collaboration can help secure external funding for dissertation research.

⁵ Ibid., 353

⁶ Ibid., 340

⁷ James P. Sampson Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition, (Florida: Florida State University, 2017) 10.

- Collaboration can provide access to difficult-to-locate measures and literature.
- Collaboration allows students to clarify their thinking and receive feedback from different perspectives.

8. What are some factors that contribute to successful dissertation research?

- All the answers below.**⁸
- Good communication, good planning, attention to detail, openness to serendipity, and visualization.
- Regularly communicating with significant others impacted by the dissertation, setting realistic goals, and utilizing an effective writing process.
- Creating and following a specific plan, using a checklist, and monitoring consistent effort.

9. What is the main purpose of the abstract in the first revised dissertation “Ensuring Sustainable Development with Changing Climate?”

- All the answers below.**⁹
- To summarize the topics and findings of the dissertations.
- To provide an overview of the structure of the research papers.
- To discuss important concepts related to climate change adaptation.

⁸ Ibid., 13 – 15.

⁹ Sara L. Traerup, “Ensuring Sustainability Development with Climate Change,” Ph.D. Diss. (Copenhagen: University of Copenhagen, 2010). 27 – 28.

10. What does the abstract of the second dissertation “The Institutionalization of Integrated Reporting: An Exploration of Adoption, Sustainability Embeddedness and Decoupling” emphasize?¹⁰

- All the answers below.**
- The exploration of institutional factors affecting integrated reporting adoption.
- The development of a measure to capture Sustainability Embeddedness in corporate reports.
- The contribution to literature on cooperate social responsibility adopting and the application of institutional theory in a novel context.

¹⁰ Mohammed E. Elmaghrabi, “The Institutionalisation of Integrated Reporting: An Exploration of Adoption, Sustainability Embeddedness and Decoupling,” Ph.D. Diss. (Stirling: University of Stirling., 2014). 2.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.